

STEROID COMPOUNDS. PART VIII. ON THE STEREOCHEMISTRY
OF MICHAEL ADDITION TO 4-METHYL-4-CARBETHOXY-
 Δ^2 -cycloHEXENONE

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Michael addition of diethyl malonate to the cyclohexenone (IV : R=Et) affords an adduct which after hydrolysis and reduction yields *cis*-1-methylcyclohexane-1-carboxy-2-acetic acid.

In connection with some problem in steroid synthesis, the steric course of the Michael addition of diethyl malonate to 4-methyl-4-carbethoxy- Δ^2 cyclohexenone was investigated. At the time this work was undertaken there was no report in the literature of this particular Michael addition, and very little data were available to permit of any prediction about the stereochemical course of the addition.

The required eneone (IV : R=Et) was prepared from the easily available keto-acid (I : R=H), described by Rubin and Vishinsky (*J. Amer. Chem. Soc.*, 1946, 68, 338). The keto-ester (I : R=Et) was brominated in cold and the resulting monobromo derivative (II : R=Et) purified by distillation. The colorless distillate, first obtained, gradually darkened on standing, and analytical values were always erratic. No attempts were made to purify it and a freshly prepared sample was always used for the next step. Attempted dehydrohalogenation with organic bases gave disappointing results and, hence, dehydrohalogenation of the corresponding ketal (III : R=Et) was tried. The cyclic ketal (III) could be readily obtained under standard conditions (Salmi, *Ber.*, 1938, 71, 1803) and was quite stable unlike the parent bromoketo-ester. On prolonged treatment with potassium *tert*-butoxide in *tert*-butyl alcohol (R. Daniels, Ph. D. thesis, Harvard University, 1950), followed by deketalisation according to Schinz and Schappi (*Helv. Chim. Acta*, 1947, 30, 1483), the unsaturated compound (IV : R=Et) was obtained in a fairly good yield.* This showed strong absorption in the infra-red at 5.8μ and 5.95μ as required for a compound of this structure.

Analysis of the compound, however, furnished high values for carbon, possibly due to *trans* esterification during alkoxide treatment. The eneone (IV : R=Et) with diethyl malonate in the presence of traces of sodium ethoxide at room temperature afforded a viscous adduct (V : R=Et) which was directly hydrolysed in the crude stage with 20% HCl, and the resulting gummy acid was purified in the form of its dimethyl ester. The keto-diester (VI : R=Me), thus obtained, was a colorless mobile oil which gave correct analysis and was characterised by a yellow 2:4-dinitrophenylhydrazone. The corresponding dibasic acid (VI : R=H), however, could not be obtained crystalline. To establish the stereochemistry of the

* The learned referee has drawn attention to a recent paper by Wanzlick *et al.* (*Chem. Ber.*, 1955, 88, 69) who have described a similar procedure for the synthesis of cyclopentenones and cyclohexenones. This paper was not available to the author at the time this manuscript was submitted. The work reported here was completed in the summer of 1951.

product, the above keto-diester was reduced according to Huang-Minlon's procedure (*J. Amer. Chem. Soc.*, 1946, **68**, 2487) to the desoxy-dicarboxylic acid (VII), m.p. 163-64°. Mixed melting point determination with an authentic specimen of *cis*-1-methylcyclohexane-1-carboxy-2-acetic acid, m.p. 163-64° did not show any depression, whereas on admixture with the *trans*-acid the melting point was considerably reduced (Linstead *et al.*, *J. Chem. Soc.*, 1936, 479, 476, 478; 1937, 1140; Bachmann and Kushner, *J. Amer. Chem. Soc.*, 1943, **65**, 1963; Woodward *et al.*, *ibid.*, 1952, **74**, 4226). No other acid could be isolated from the mother-liquors left after removal of the *cis*-acid. The addition of malonic ester, therefore proceeded in a stereospecific manner to yield the *cis*-adduct (V: R=Et).

After the completion of this work, Nazarov and Zevyalov (*Chem. Abst.*, 1953, **47**, 10515) described the methyl ester of 4-methyl-4-carboxy- Δ^2 -cyclohexenone (IV: R=Me) from the bromo compound (II: R=Me) which they prepared by a different route. The Russian chemists dehydrohalogenated their bromo compound with diethylaniline at 150° and obtained good results. In our hands dehydrohalogenation by this procedure was never satisfactory. Nazarov also added diethyl malonate to the enone (IV:R=Me) and obtained an adduct stereochemistry of which, however, was not defined.

(I)

(II)

(III)

(IV)

(V)

(VI)

(VII)

A plausible explanation for the observed stereospecificity to provide the *cis*-isomer in the above Michael addition may be as follows. In the original cyclohexanone derivative (I), the bulkier carboxyl group must be placed in the stable equatorial and the methyl group in the axial position. In the cyclohexanone compound (IV), they will take up the half-equatorial (*e'*) and the half-axial (*a'*) positions (Barton, *Chem. Ind.*, 1954, 21). The steric effect is then asserted by the axial (*a'*) methyl group which directs the incoming malonate anion to approach from the side away from it, and this is perhaps somewhat favoured by the electrostatic attraction of the malonate anion to the side of the carboxyl group. The net result is then the axial addition of the malonate group to the ring system, and this picture is in agreement with Corey's bromination experiments in cyclohexanone compounds as well with the theoretical considerations of maximum overlap of the

p-orbitals (Corey, *J. Amer. Chem. Soc.*, 1954, **76**, 175). The reported cases (Abc *et al.*, *Proc. Japan Acad.*, 1954, **30**, 116, 119; Ralls, *J. Amer. Chem. Soc.*, 1953, **75**, 2123; Shoppee and Stephenson, *J. Chem. Soc.*, 1954 2230), where in the Michael addition the malonate residue has taken up the equatorial position, could be due to thermodynamic considerations, since the Michael addition is a reversible reaction and in the absence of other steric factors operating the more stable isomer with the bulkier group in equatorial position is likely to predominate in equilibrium (cf. Corey, *J. Amer. Chem. Soc.*, 1955, **77**, 1045).

EXPERIMENTAL

Ethyl 4-Methyl-4-carboxy-2-bromocyclohexanone (II: R=Et).—Ethyl 4-methyl-4-carboxycyclohexanone (I: R=Et) was prepared from the corresponding keto-acid (I: R=H; Rubin and Wishinky, *loc. cit.*) in the usual way by esterification with EtOH—H₂SO₄ mixture, b.p. 80°–85°/0.5 mm. (Found: C, 64.91; H, 8.77. C₁₆H₂₄O₃ requires C, 65.21; H, 8.69 per cent).

The above keto-ester (36.6 g.) in dry chloroform (300 c.c.) was cooled in ice and bromine (32 g.), dissolved in chloroform (75 c.c.), was added dropwise with shaking. After the addition was complete the mixture was poured into ice and the chloroform layer removed and then washed with dilute sodium bicarbonate solution, water and dried. The residue, left after removal of the chloroform, was fractionated under reduced pressure. After a fore-run of the unchanged keto-ester, the bromo compound distilled at 110°–120°/0.5 mm. as a colorless heavy liquid. On redistillation, the major fraction distilled at 113–15°/0.5 mm., yield 32 g. The initially obtained colorless distillate gradually developed a brown to pink colour which deepened on standing. No satisfactory analysis could be obtained and it was used directly for the next step.

2-Bromo-4-methyl-4-carbomethoxycyclohexane-1-spiro-2':1':3'-dioxolan (III: R=Et).—A mixture of the above bromo compound (32 g.), ethyleneglycol (8.4 g.) in dry benzene (160 c.c.) and *p*-toluenesulphonic acid (0.3 g.) was refluxed for 5 hours in a flask fitted with a water separator. The mixture was then cooled, poured into dilute sodium bicarbonate solution and the benzene layer removed, washed with water, dried and concentrated. The residue distilled at 100°–105°/0.3 mm. as a colorless mobile oil, yield 26 g. The ketal was quite stable and did not develop any coloration on standing. (Found: C, 47.58; H, 6.35. C₁₂H₁₈O₄Br requires C, 46.90; H, 6.18 per cent).

Ethyl-4-methyl-4-carboxy-Δ²-cyclohexenone (IV: R=Et).—To a solution of potassium *tert*-butoxide, prepared from metallic potassium (3.2 g.) and *tert*-butyl alcohol (70 c. c.), the above bromoketal (III, 25 g.) was added all at once and the mixture refluxed under nitrogen for 40 hours. At the end of this period the dark liquid was concentrated under reduced pressure, cooled and poured into water. The organic matter was extracted with ether, and the residue, left after removal of the ether, was heated for 3 hours with dry acetone (150 c.c.) and *p*-toluenesulphonic acid (0.5 g.). Acetone was then distilled off, the residue poured into water, extracted with ether several times and the combined ether extract washed with dilute sodium bicarbonate solution, then with water and finally dried over anhydrous sodium

sulphate. The residue obtained after removal of ether distilled as a colorless mobile liquid, b.p. 80° - $85^{\circ}/0.3$ mm., yield 10 g. A small fraction was redistilled and the middle cut collected for analysis. {Found: C, 67.04; H, 8.63. $C_{11}H_{14}O_3$ requires C, 65.43; H, 8.78 and $C_{12}H_{16}O_3$ [IV: $R=C(CH_3)_2$] requires C, 68.57; H, 8.57 per cent}. Sharp bands in the infra-red at 5.8μ and 5.95μ correspond to the ester and the cyclohexenone grouping. A red 2:4-dinitrophenylhydrazone was formed, but it separated as a gum and could not be easily obtained crystalline.

cis-Dimethyl-4-methyl-4-carboxycyclohexanone-3-acetic Acid (VI: $R=Me$).—The unsaturated ester, obtained above (9.5 g.), was added to an ice-cold mixture of diethyl malonate (10 g.) and sodium ethoxide in absolute alcohol, prepared from sodium (0.025 g.) and alcohol (15 c.c.). An immediate brown colour developed. The mixture was left overnight at room temperature and then decomposed with ice and acetic acid. The organic matter was taken up in ether and washed with dilute sodium carbonate solution, water and dried over anhydrous sodium sulphate. The viscous residue, left after removal of the ether, could not be distilled owing to decomposition. It was hydrolysed as such with 20% HCl for 20 hours. The aqueous solution was then completely evaporated to dryness and the residual gum esterified with absolute methanol (100 c.c.) and H_2SO_4 (d. 1.84, 6 c.c.) for 10 hours. The ester was isolated in the usual way and purified by distillation, b.p. $128-30^{\circ}/0.5$ mm. (Found: C, 59.65; H, 7.94. $C_{12}H_{16}O_5$ requires C, 59.50; H, 7.43 per cent). A higher boiling residue remained in the distilling flask.

The keto-ester readily furnished a yellow 2:4-dinitrophenylhydrazone, m.p. 154° after crystallisation from alcohol. (Found: C, 50.92; H, 5.69. $C_{18}H_{22}O_6N_4$ requires C, 51.18; H, 5.21 per cent). The corresponding dibasic acid (VI: $R=H$) could not be obtained crystalline.

cis-1-Methylcyclohexane-1-carboxy-2-acetic Acid (VII).—The above keto-ester (VI: $R=Me$; 1 g.), trimethyleneglycol (9 c.c.), hydrazine hydrate (85%, 0.9 c.c.) and powdered KOH (1 g.), intimately mixed, were heated for 2 hours under reflux and then strongly heated without any condenser until temperature of the liquid reached 205° . It was maintained around this temperature for 4 hours and then cooled, diluted with water and poured into iced hydrochloric acid. This was then extracted several times with ether and the ether extract after one washing with water was concentrated. The residual brown gum solidified in contact with a little benzene and scratching. After crystallisation from dilute acetic acid the melting point was $163-64^{\circ}$. Mixed melting point with an authentic sample of *cis*-1-methylcyclohexane-1-carboxy-2-acetic acid, m. p. $163-64^{\circ}$, was not depressed, but with the *trans*-acid, m. p. $176-77^{\circ}$, the melting point was depressed to $140-42^{\circ}$.

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